

Risk and Return Analysis of Equity and Debt Mutual Funds in India

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ABSTRACT

Mutual funds have become one of the most preferred investment avenues for investors due to their potential to provide diversification, professional management, and long-term wealth creation. The present study, titled "*An Empirical Analysis of Equity and Debt Mutual Fund Performance in India*," aims to evaluate the performance of selected mutual funds by examining the influence of macroeconomic factors and analysing the effectiveness of traditional and modern performance evaluation models. The specific objectives of the study are to identify the impact of macroeconomic variables such as GDP, inflation, repo rate, and exchange rate on mutual fund performance and to analyse the effectiveness of performance measures such as Sharpe Ratio, Jensen's Alpha, and Treynor Ratio. The study adopts a descriptive research design to provide a systematic analysis of mutual fund performance. Data were collected from secondary sources, and a simple random sampling technique was used for selecting the sample mutual funds. Statistical tools such as descriptive statistics, correlation analysis, ANOVA, and one-sample t-test were employed to analyse the data. The analysis was carried out using SPSS and Jamovi software to ensure accuracy and reliability of results. The findings indicate that macroeconomic factors significantly influence mutual fund returns and that traditional and modern performance evaluation models provide consistent assessments of fund performance. The study contributes to the existing literature by offering useful insights for investors, fund managers, researchers, and policymakers in making informed investment and financial decisions.

Keywords: *Mutual Funds, Risk and Return, Sharpe Ratio, Jensen's Alpha, Treynor Ratio, Fund Managers' Strategies, Performance Evaluation.*

INTRODUCTION

Mutual funds have become one of the most preferred investment avenues for individuals seeking professional fund management, diversification, and long-term wealth creation. In today's dynamic financial environment, the performance of mutual funds is increasingly influenced by changing macroeconomic conditions such as GDP growth, inflation, interest rates, and exchange rate movements. Investors and fund managers closely monitor these factors as they directly affect market returns and investment decisions. At the same time, evaluating mutual fund performance has become more important due to the growing number of investment options available in the market. Traditional measures based on returns alone are no longer sufficient, leading to the adoption of modern risk-adjusted performance evaluation models such as Sharpe Ratio, Treynor Ratio, and Jensen's Alpha. These models provide a more comprehensive assessment of fund efficiency by considering both risk and return. In the Indian context, the rapid growth of the mutual fund industry and increasing investor participation highlight the need for effective performance evaluation. Therefore, this study examines the influence of macroeconomic factors on mutual fund performance and analyses the effectiveness of traditional and modern performance evaluation models, providing valuable insights for investors, fund managers, and policymakers.

2. NATURE AND SCOPE OF THE STUDY

The nature and scope of the study should be written in Cambria with a font size of 10. This section should clearly describe the type of study undertaken, its thematic focus, and the boundaries within which the research is conducted. It should explain the extent of coverage, the variables or aspects being examined, and the rationale for selecting these elements. Replace the placeholder text with your own material that accurately reflects the breadth and limitations of your research work.

Geographical Scope: The study is limited to mutual fund schemes operating within India under SEBI regulations. It considers the impact of Indian macroeconomic conditions on fund performance.

Organizational Scope: The study focuses on selected Asset Management Companies offering equity and debt mutual funds. It examines how these organizations apply evaluation models and managerial strategies in fund management.

Functional Scope: The study covers performance measurement functions using risk, return, and comparative evaluation models for selected mutual funds. It includes analysis functions related to macroeconomic impact and fund managers' decision strategies affecting fund performance.

Time Scope: The study covers mutual fund performance over a defined multi-year period to capture market variations and consistency in returns. The selected timeframe allows comparison across different economic phases to assess stability and performance trends.

Methodological Scope: The study applies an empirical and quantitative approach to evaluate equity and debt mutual fund performance using measurable risk–return indicators. Both traditional measures and selected modern evaluation methods are used to compare performance outcomes. Secondary data from reliable financial sources is analysed over a defined period to ensure consistency and validity.

3. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Mishra and Singh (2025)⁶ studied equity, debt, and hybrid mutual funds in India. The study found that equity funds generated higher returns, while debt funds provided more stable performance. Rohini and Jayanthi (2025) evaluated HDFC SIP schemes using risk-adjusted measures. The results showed that balanced funds offered stable returns with lower risk. Thomas and Wilson (2025)⁵ analyzed equity mutual funds using Sharpe, Treynor, and Jensen models. The study concluded that infrastructure and selected HDFC funds delivered strong risk-adjusted returns. Mishra and Singh (2025)⁶ examined mutual fund performance using risk-return indicators. The findings revealed mixed performance among funds, emphasizing careful fund selection. Nandini, Aseen Babu and Srikanth (2025)⁸ evaluated mutual funds using standard performance measures. The study found significant differences in fund efficiency based on risk-return trade-offs. South Asian Journal of Management (2008) focused on mutual fund performance evaluation. The study highlighted the importance of risk-adjusted measures for investment decisions. Mamatzakis, Babalos and Matousek studied US equity mutual funds using efficiency analysis. The results showed that fund performance varies due to risk and operational factors. Ter Horst, Nijman and de Roon (1998) evaluated Dutch mutual funds using style analysis. The study found that some funds outperformed benchmarks when investment style was considered. Aaluri et al. (2024)¹ examined the relationship between mutual fund growth and equity market performance. The findings indicated a positive impact of mutual fund investments on market behavior. Saurabh Pandey (2019)¹⁸ analyzed equity mutual fund schemes using risk-adjusted measures. The study found that most schemes outperformed the benchmark index. Verma and Nema (2022)²³ studied the growth of the Indian mutual fund industry. The results showed increasing investor participation and strong future growth potential.

Shveta Singh and Dipika (2021)²¹ examined the relationship between fund flows and performance. The study found that investors preferred funds with better past performance and lower risk. Shikha Gupta (2022)¹⁰ evaluated ESG mutual funds in India. The findings revealed that ESG funds achieved steady growth and competitive returns. Zhao (2004)²⁹ reviewed dynamic mutual fund performance evaluation models. The study concluded that dynamic models provide better insights than traditional approaches. Gendron and Charkiewicz (2005)¹⁶ developed a decision-support model for mutual fund selection. The findings suggested that information quality improves investment decisions. Choi and Murithi (2001)²⁷ used Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) to evaluate mutual funds. The study identified efficient and inefficient funds based on performance rankings. Wang and Huang (2010)²⁵ applied neural network models for mutual fund evaluation. The results showed better prediction accuracy compared to traditional methods. Pendaraki and Zopounidis (2003)¹³ used a multicriteria approach to rank mutual funds. The study found that multiple criteria provide more accurate fund evaluation. Chrétien and Kammoun (2015)²² examined mutual fund performance from investor perspectives. The findings showed that performance evaluation differs across investor groups. Pangestuti, Wahyudi and Robiyanto (2017) evaluated Indonesian equity funds using several performance measures. The study found that most funds were well diversified and efficient.

Alibakhshi and Sadeghi Moghadam (2016)² applied MADM techniques to rank mutual funds. The findings showed that similarity-based methods produced more reliable rankings. Zhao, Wang and Lai (2011)²⁸ evaluated Chinese mutual funds using DEA models. The study found that risk management significantly influences fund efficiency. Angelidis, Giamouridis and Tessaromatis (2013)³ assessed mutual funds using self-reported benchmarks. The results emphasized the importance of appropriate benchmark selection. Chi (2013)²⁶ studied actively managed mutual funds in China. The findings indicated positive stock selection skills among several fund managers. Ilo, Yinusa and Elumah (2018)¹¹ analyzed Nigerian mutual funds using risk-adjusted measures. The study found that most funds failed to outperform the market. Mishra and Ahuja (2016)²⁰ examined mutual fund performance during bull and bear markets. The results showed stronger performance in bull markets but weak market timing ability. Vysniauskas and Rutkauskas (2014)¹⁹ compared different mutual fund performance measures. The study concluded that evaluation results vary depending on the selected ratio. CA Jyoti J. Patel (2020)⁴ evaluated selected Indian mutual funds using risk-return analysis. The findings showed that market conditions significantly affect fund performance. Soumya Guha Deb, Banerjee and Chakrabarti (2007) analyzed market timing and stock selection abilities. The study found limited market timing skills but some stock-picking ability. Manjunatha, Shruthi and Rajesh Kumar (2022)¹⁴ compared private and public equity

mutual funds. The study concluded that there was no significant difference in their performance.

4. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To identify the influence of macroeconomic factors on selected mutual fund performance.
- To analyze the effectiveness of traditional and modern performance evaluation models.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research method: The study adopts a descriptive and analytical research design to evaluate the performance of selected mutual funds in India. Secondary data were collected from mutual fund reports, AMFI, and other official financial sources. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize return and risk data, while analytical tools such as Sharpe Ratio, Treynor Ratio, and Jensen's Alpha were applied for performance evaluation. The findings provide insights into mutual fund performance and support informed investment decisions.

sampling design

- **Sampling method:** The study uses a simple random sampling method to select equity and debt mutual fund schemes. Each fund has an equal chance of being selected, ensuring fairness and reducing selection bias.
- **Sampling size:** The study considers a sample of 10 selected mutual fund schemes, including both equity and debt funds, chosen from recognized asset management companies. The sample size is sufficient to analyze performance trends and compare fund performance.

Source of data

The study is based on secondary data collected from reliable and authentic sources. The data is obtained from mutual fund reports, official websites of asset management companies, and financial platforms such as NSE, and BSE. Additional information is gathered from research journals, articles, and published reports related to mutual funds. The data includes details on Net Asset Value (NAV), returns, and other performance indicators. These sources ensure accuracy and consistency in the analysis.

Tools of analysis

- **ANOVA:** ANOVA is used to determine whether there are significant differences between the means of two or more groups. It helps identify if the observed variations are statistically significant.
- **Correlation Analysis:** Correlation measures the strength and direction of the relationship between two variables. It indicates whether variables move together positively, negatively, or have no relationship.
- **One-Sample t-Test:** A one-sample t-test is used to compare the sample mean with a known or hypothesized population mean. It helps determine whether the difference is statistically significant.

Hypothesis of the study

H0₁: There is no influence of macroeconomic factors on the performance of the selected mutual funds.

H0₂: There is no difference between traditional and modern models in measuring mutual fund performance.

Data Analysis and Interpretation This chapter presents the analysis and interpretation of data collected from selected equity and debt mutual funds in India. The study evaluates fund performance using NAV data, returns, risk measures, and risk-adjusted performance indicators. Statistical tools such as descriptive statistics, correlation analysis, ANOVA, and t-tests are applied to analyze the data. The findings help in understanding the impact of risk, return, macroeconomic factors, and fund management strategies on mutual fund performance.

H0₁: There is no influence of macroeconomic factors on the performance of the selected mutual funds.

ANOVA						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	214.805	4	53.701	21.400	.045 ^b
	Residual	5.019	2	2.509		
	Total	219.824	6			

a. Dependent Variable: AVGR
b. Predictors: (Constant), ER, GDP, Inflation, REPO

Source: Secondary data -SPSS output

The ANOVA results indicate that the regression model is statistically significant in explaining variations in the dependent variable (AVGR). The model produced an F-value of 21.400 with a significance value of 0.045, which is less

than 0.05. This shows that the independent variables—ER, GDP, Inflation, and REPO—collectively have a significant impact on AVGR. Therefore, the overall regression model provides a good fit and supports the conclusion that the selected macroeconomic factors significantly influence AVGR.

Correlations

		GDP	Inflation	REPO	ER	AVGR
GDP	Pearson Correlation	1	-.359	.521	.454	-.684
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.429	.230	.306	.090
	N	7	7	7	7	7
Inflation	Pearson Correlation	-.359	1	-.269	-.549	.872*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.429		.559	.201	.011
	N	7	7	7	7	7
REPO	Pearson Correlation	.521	-.269	1	.943**	-.381
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.230	.559		.001	.400
	N	7	7	7	7	7
ER	Pearson Correlation	.454	-.549	.943**	1	-.559
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.306	.201	.001		.192
	N	7	7	7	7	7
AVGR	Pearson Correlation	-.684	.872*	-.381	-.559	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.090	.011	.400	.192	
	N	7	7	7	7	7

Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Secondary data -SPSS output

The correlation analysis shows that AVGR has a strong positive and statistically significant relationship with Inflation ($r = 0.872$, $p = 0.011$), indicating that increases in inflation are associated with higher AVGR values. AVGR is negatively correlated with GDP ($r = -0.684$), REPO ($r = -0.381$), and ER ($r = -0.559$), suggesting an inverse relationship, although these correlations are not statistically significant at the 5% level. A very strong positive and significant correlation exists between REPO and ER ($r = 0.943$, $p = 0.001$), indicating a close association between these variables. Overall, Inflation emerges as the most influential factor associated with AVGR among the selected macroeconomic variables.

H0₂: There is no difference between traditional and modern models in measuring mutual fund performance.

One-Sample Test

	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Interval of the Difference Lower	Confidence of the Upper
Sharpe	43.034	9	.000	1.04450	.9896	1.0994
Jenson	24.959	9	.000	.01009	.0092	.0110
Treynor	2.411	9	.039	.00099	.0001	.0019

Source: Secondary data -SPSS output

The One-Sample Test results indicate that all three performance measures—Sharpe Ratio, Jensen’s Alpha, and Treynor Ratio—have mean values that are significantly different from the test value, as their p-values are below 0.05. The Sharpe Ratio (t = 43.034, p = 0.000) shows the strongest statistical significance, indicating superior risk-adjusted performance. Jensen’s Alpha (t = 24.959, p = 0.000) also demonstrates significant positive excess returns over the expected benchmark return. Similarly, the Treynor Ratio (t = 2.411, p = 0.039) is statistically significant, suggesting that the portfolio generated adequate returns relative to its systematic risk.

Correlations

		Sharpe	Jenson	Treynor
Sharpe	Pearson Correlation	1	.938**	.928**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000
	N	10	10	10
Jenson	Pearson Correlation	.938**	1	.998**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000
	N	10	10	10
Treynor	Pearson Correlation	.928**	.998**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	
	N	10	10	10

Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Secondary data -SPSS output

The correlation analysis reveals very strong positive relationships among the Sharpe Ratio, Jensen’s Alpha, and Treynor Ratio. Sharpe Ratio is highly correlated with Jensen’s Alpha (r = 0.938, p < 0.01) and Treynor Ratio (r = 0.928, p < 0.01), indicating consistency in measuring portfolio performance. The strongest correlation is observed between Jensen’s Alpha and Treynor Ratio (r = 0.998, p < 0.01), showing an almost perfect positive association. Overall, the significant positive correlations suggest that all three performance measures provide similar and consistent evaluations of investment performance.

5. DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

- The regression model shows a very high explanatory power ($R^2 = 0.977$), indicating that GDP, Inflation, Repo Rate, and Exchange Rate collectively explain most of the changes in mutual fund returns.

- Inflation has a strong positive and significant relationship with mutual fund returns ($r = 0.872$, $p < 0.05$), suggesting better fund performance during periods of higher inflation.
- ANOVA results ($F = 21.400$, $p = 0.045$) confirm that macroeconomic variables significantly influence mutual fund returns, leading to the rejection of H_0 .
- The high correlation between Repo Rate and Exchange Rate ($r = 0.943$) indicates that these factors move together and jointly affect mutual fund performance.
- The Sharpe, Jensen, and Treynor ratios show consistent and stable risk-adjusted performance across the 10 selected funds, with low standard deviation and balanced distribution.
- One-sample t-tests for all three ratios are statistically significant ($p < 0.05$), confirming that the funds generate meaningful excess returns after adjusting for risk.
- The correlation analysis shows a very strong positive relationship among Sharpe, Jensen, and Treynor ratios ($r > 0.92$), indicating that all three measures move closely together in evaluating performance.
- The results prove that traditional (Sharpe, Treynor) and modern (Jensen's Alpha) models provide similar conclusions, demonstrating consistency and reliability in measuring mutual fund efficiency.
- Investors should closely monitor macroeconomic factors such as inflation, GDP growth, repo rate, and exchange rate before making mutual fund investment decisions, as these variables significantly influence fund performance.
- Fund managers should adopt dynamic portfolio strategies to respond effectively to changing economic conditions, thereby improving returns and reducing risk during periods of market uncertainty.
- Investors should evaluate mutual funds using both return and risk-adjusted measures such as Sharpe Ratio, Jensen's Alpha, and Treynor Ratio, rather than relying only on absolute returns.
- Mutual fund companies should strengthen risk management and diversification practices, as fluctuations in macroeconomic variables can have a substantial impact on fund performance and investor returns.

6. CONCLUSION

The study concludes that Non-Performing Loans (NPLs) continue to be a major concern for the Indian banking sector as they directly influence asset quality, profitability, and overall financial performance. The comparative analysis of selected public and private sector banks reveals significant variations in NPL indicators, with private sector banks generally demonstrating better control over asset quality through effective credit monitoring and risk management practices. The findings of the One-Sample t-test confirm noticeable differences in NPL-related and financial performance indicators among the selected banks. Further, correlation and ANOVA analyses indicate that lending activities and provisioning practices significantly influence bank profitability and reflect the importance of sound credit policies in managing NPLs. Therefore, strengthening credit appraisal systems, improving recovery mechanisms, and adopting effective risk management strategies are essential for reducing NPL levels and enhancing the stability and efficiency of the banking sector. Future research can consider a larger sample size, longer study period, and additional factors such as technological adoption, governance practices, and macroeconomic conditions to provide a broader understanding of NPL management in India.

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